

INTEGRATION OF IOT DEVICES INTO TELECOMMUNICATION MONITORING SYSTEMS

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ANNOTATION.

This article provides an overview of the basic concepts and principles underlying the integration of smart devices in telecommunications. This publication also examines the importance of using IoT technologies to improve the effectiveness of monitoring in telecommunications systems. During the study of this topic, general trends in the development of IoT and its impact on modern telecommunications monitoring systems are considered, work schemes and practical applications of IoT devices are presented, standards and protocols are analyzed and key aspects of integrating smart devices into the telecommunications infrastructure are discussed.

KEYWORDS: Internet of things, integration, wireless communications, LoRaWAN, Zigbee, Wi-Fi, protocols and standards.

INTRODUCTION.

The integration of Internet of Things (IoT) devices into telecommunication systems has become one of the key factors in their development in the context of the rapid growth of data volumes and automation needs. Integration is the process of combining individual elements, parts, or systems into a single whole so that they work together and efficiently. IoT devices equipped with sensors, processors and communication tools open up new possibilities for monitoring and managing networks. They provide real-time data collection, network status analysis and timely response to changes, which increases the overall efficiency of the telecommunications infrastructure. Every year the number of IoT devices increases, which requires the development and implementation of new monitoring methods. These devices have already found their application in the management of cellular and fiber-optic networks, as well as in smart city systems, where they help monitor the operation of Wi-Fi networks, surveillance cameras and other infrastructure elements. Thanks to IoT, it has become possible to predict failures, detect overloads and optimize traffic routing in real time. However, the process of integrating IoT into telecommunications involves certain challenges. Issues of security, hardware compatibility and processing of large amounts of data require a detailed approach and innovative solutions. Nevertheless, the potential for using IoT in this area is huge, and their implementation contributes to the creation of more reliable and scalable networks. [1]

Figure 1. The number of active IoT and non-IoT connections worldwide from 2010 to 2025 in billions.

The principles of IoT devices and their application in telecommunications.

The principles of operation of IoT devices in telecommunications include data collection using various sensors, their transmission through a communication network, processing and analysis of the information received. These devices can be used to monitor the condition of equipment, manage energy consumption, optimize processes and improve the quality of service. In telecommunications, IoT devices allow you to collect data on network operation, measure the quality of service, predict failures and improve overall system performance [2]. Thus, the integration of IoT devices into telecommunication systems can improve the efficiency, reliability and security of the network.

Principles of operation of IoT devices are sensors, activators, and other electronic components connected to a network to exchange data and perform tasks. The basic principles of their work include:

Figure 2. The scheme of operation of IoT devices.

Communication technologies for integrating IoT devices into monitoring systems.

Various communication technologies are widely used to integrate IoT devices into telecommunications monitoring systems. One of the most common technologies is wireless data transmission via Wi-Fi, Bluetooth and Zigbee protocols. These technologies provide a reliable connection between devices and monitoring systems [3]. In addition, there are specialized industrial communication protocols such as LoRa and NB-IoT, which provide long-range data transmission and low power consumption. For telecommunications monitoring

systems, especially on a large scale, it is also important to be able to use cable communication technologies such as Ethernet to ensure stable and high-speed data transmission.

Table 1. Communication technologies for the integration of iOS devices

Communication technologies	Advantages:	Disadvantages:	Usage
Wi-Fi	High data transfer rate. Wide compatibility with existing devices. Easy to set up and use.	Short range (up to 10-30 m). Limited bandwidth.	Personal devices, smart watches, medical sensors.
Zigbee и Z-Wave	Low power consumption. Stable operation in networks with a large number of devices. Support for working in "mesh" networks to increase the range of action.	Low data transfer rate. Requires compatible gateways.	Smart homes, lighting and climate control systems.
LPWAN (Low Power Wide Area Network): LoRaWAN, Sigfox	Very low power consumption. Long range (up to 10-15 km).	Low bandwidth. Limited infrastructure availability in some regions.	Smart agriculture, environmental monitoring systems, water and energy level sensors.
Cellular networks (2G, 3G, 4G, 5G)	Wide coverage area. High data transfer rate Wide coverage area. High data transfer rate	High power consumption. Dependence on the infrastructure of the telecom operator.	Transport systems, video surveillance systems, car trackers.
NB-IoT (Narrowband IoT)	Optimized for iOS devices. Low connection cost. A large number of connections in a small area.	Dependence on mobile operators. Low data transfer rate.	Monitoring of utility resources, smart meters, security systems.
RFID и NFC	Ultra-low power consumption. High accuracy for short distances.	Limited range (usually up to 10 cm for NFS). Not applicable for transferring large amounts of data.	Logistics, access control, contactless payments.

Protocols and standards for the interaction of IoT devices and monitoring systems.

Among the main protocols for communication between devices and monitoring systems are MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport), CoAP (Constrained Application Protocol) and HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol). Protocols such as DTLS (Datagram Transport Layer

Security) and TLS (Transport Layer Security) can be used to ensure the security of data transmission. It is also important to take into account standards, for example, de facto standards of open hardware manufacturers such as Zigbee and Bluetooth, as well as industry standards from IEEE and IETF, which establish requirements for interfaces and protocols for the interaction of IoT devices and monitoring systems. The most active work at all levels of the Internet of Things is in the field of standardization. Today, large organizations such as the IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) are engaged in the development of standards and ISO/IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission). In mid-2014, the first IEEE P2413 working Group began developing the "Architectural Framework Standard for IoT"[4].

CONCLUSION

As a result of the study, it was found that the integration of iOS devices into telecommunications monitoring systems has significant potential to improve monitoring processes and ensure more efficient operation of telecommunications systems. The main results of the study showed that communication technologies, monitoring system architecture, protocols and standards play an important role in the successful integration of IoT devices. In addition, data security and privacy remain key aspects when integrating iOS devices. The study also revealed the potential of using machine learning and data analytics to optimize monitoring systems. Despite the challenges associated with the development of IoT technologies, the prospects for integrating iOS devices into telecommunications monitoring systems remain encouraging.

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